

1-(*N*-*t*.butyl-*N'*-phenylformamidino)-1-*t*.butyl-3-phenylthiocarbamide (VI) which on further oxidation with bromine afforded the related *N*(2-benzothiazolyl)-*t*.butyl-*N'*-phenyl-*N''*-*t*.butylguanidine (VII). These changes can be shown as follows:

On oxidation with thionyl chloride in a chloroform medium, VII was the sole product isolated. On boiling with hydrochloric acid, it decomposed into *t*-butyl chloride, phenylcarbamide and 2-aminobenzothiazole which confirms its structure (VII).

EXPERIMENTAL

The 1-*t*.butyl-3-phenylthiocarbamide was prepared from *t*.butyl isothiocyanate² and aniline according to Nair's³ procedure.

Oxidation with Bromine in Chloroform.—1-*t*.butyl-3-phenylthiocarbamide (4 g.) was suspended in dry chloroform (25 ml.) and bromine (0.8 ml.) dissolved in a small quantity of chloroform was added with cooling and stirring. On standing for 24 hr. a crystalline solid (2 g.), m.p. 240° separated. On basification of the aqueous solution, a water crystallizable base, m.p. 130°, was obtained. It afforded a picrate, m.p. 265°. The product was identified as the hydrobromide of 2-aminobenzothiazole (I) through mixed m.p. with an authentic sample and by other derivatives.

Oxidation with Bromine in aq. Ethanol.—1-*t*.butyl-3-phenylthiocarbamide (4 g.) was dissolved in aqueous ethanol (30 ml.) and bromine (1.3 ml. dissolved in 20 ml. aqueous ethanol) was added gradually with constant stirring over a period of 30 min. Elemental sulphur was found to separate. The reaction mixture on standing overnight was filtered free from sulphur, cooled and basified when a soft solid base was precipitated (5.5 g), m.p. 90-95°.

A part of the base was dissolved in minimum quantity of ethanol and filtered in cold conc. hydrobromic acid when a crystalline hydrobromide was precipitated. It was purified by dissolving in absolute ethanol and reprecipitation with conc. hydrobromic acid, m.p. 110° (Found: N 10.7, S 5.4%, equiv. 274.5; $C_{12}H_{15}N_4S, 2HBr$ requires N 10.3, S 5.7% and equiv., 272). On reaction with sodium nitrite in an aqueous medium it formed a nitroso derivative, m.p. 78°. When warmed with dilute alkali it decomposed and amongst the products, 1-*t*.butyl-3-phenylthiocarbamide (m.p. 125°) was identified. This dihydrobromide was found identical with the dihydrobromide of bis-*t*.butyl-phenylformamidino sulphide (III) (*vide infra*).

2. E. Schmidt, W. Striewsky, M. Seefelder, and F. Hitzler, *Liebigs Ann.*, 1950, 568, 192.

3. G. V. Nair, *Ind. Jour. Chem.*, 1966, 4, 516.

The other part of the crude base (m.p. 90-95°) on extraction with cold benzene left a residue which crystallised from aq. ethanol, and had m.p. 165°. (Found: C 68.3, H 8.3, N 14.3; $C_{11}H_{10}N_2O$ requires C 68.8, H 8.4, N 14.5%). On boiling with conc. HCl it afforded phenyl carbamide (m.p. 147°) and t. butylchloride as indicated by its greenish smoky flame. It was, therefore, identified as 1-t. butyl-3-phenylcarbamide (IV).

If excess of bromine was used, another product crystallisable from ethanol, m.p. 197°, was obtained (Found: C 47.9, H 5.3, N 10.2, Br 30.0; $C_{11}H_{13}N_2OBr$ requires C 48.5, H 5.5, N 10.3 and Br 29.6%). The same product (V) was obtained by the bromination of the above described 1-t. butyl-3-phenylcarbamide. On boiling with conc. HCl, it liberated t. butyl chloride and formed *p*-bromophenyl carbamide, identified through its undepressed mixed m.p. with an authentic sample, m.p.⁴ 270°, prepared from *p*-bromoaniline and carbamide⁵. Thus the product was identified as 1-*p*-bromophenyl-3-t. butyl carbamide (V).

Synthesis of bis-t. Butylphenylformamidine Sulphide Dihydrobromide (III).—N-t. butyl N'-phenyl formamidine chloride (1 g), m.p. 105°; (Found: N 13.6, equiv., 207.5; $C_{11}H_{13}N_2Cl$ requires N 13.3%, equiv., 210, obtained by the action of hydrogen chloride on phenyl-t. butylcarbodiimide⁶ in an acetone medium) and 1-t. butyl-3-phenyl thiocarbamide (2 g.) were dissolved in a small quantity of absolute ethanol and treated with conc. aq. HBr (5 ml) with cooling. A sticky solid was obtained which on repeated treatment with toluene became granular (2.5 g). It was purified by dissolving in absolute ethanol and reprecipitation with conc. HBr and had m.p. 110°. It did not depress the m.p. of the hydrobromide described in the previous experiment (Found: N 10.6, S 5.4, equiv., 274; $C_{22}H_{30}N_4S$, 2HBr requires N 10.3, S 5.9% and equiv., 272).

If in the above experiment hydrogen chloride was used in place of hydrobromic acid and acetone was substituted as solvent, dihydrochloride of the bis-t. butylphenyl formamidine sulphide was obtained, m.p. 105° (Found: N 12.6, S 7.7, equiv., 224.2; $C_{22}H_{30}N_4S$, 2HCl requires N 12.3, S 7.3% and equiv., 227.5).

The same dihydrochloride was formed if phenyl cyanamide and 1-t. butyl-3-phenylthiocarbamide were used (cf 7,⁸)

Isomerisation of bis-t. Butylphenylformamidine Sulphide Dihydrobromide into 1-(N-t. butyl-N'-phenylformamido)1-t. butyl-3-phenyl Thiocarbamide (VI).—1 gm. of the sulphide (III) was heated under reflux with methanol (10 ml) for 15 min. On cooling, a crystalline solid (0.6 g), m.p. 140°, was obtained (Found: N 12.5, S 6.6, equiv., 459; $C_{22}H_{30}N_4S$, HBr requires N 12.1, S 6.9%, equiv., 462). This was most probably the related amidinothiocarbamide (VI) as on oxidation with bromine in an ethanolic medium it afforded a base, m.p. 168°, identified as the related benzothiazolyl guanidine (VII) (*vide infra*).

Oxidation of 1-t. Butyl-3-phenylthiocarbamide with Thionyl Chloride.—1-t. butyl-3-phenylthiocarbamide (3 g.) was dissolved in dry chloroform (35 ml.) and a solution of thionyl chloride (3 ml.) in chloroform (10 ml.) was added gradually with cooling and shaking

4. F. B. Dains and E. Werthem. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 2303.

5. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry.", 1954, 617.

6. H. G. Khorana, *Chem. Rev.*, 1953, 53, 145.

7. S. N. Pandeya, *Ind. Jour. Chem.*, 1964, 2, 440.

8. M. G. Paranjpe, *This Journal*, 1966, 43, 45.

After standing for 24 hr., the solvent was evaporated and the sticky residue dissolved in water when elemental sulphur was found to separate. On filtration and basification of the filtrate, a solid base (2 g.) was obtained, crystallised from ethanol/benzene and had m.p. 168° (Found: C 68.66, H 8.13, N 14.42, S 8.2; $C_{12}H_{10}N_4S$ requires C 69.4, H 7.3, N 14.7, S 8.4%). It afforded a hydrobromide, m.p. 205° (Found: N 12.4, S 7.2, equiv., 458; $C_{12}H_{10}N_4S.HBr$ requires N 12.1, S 6.9%; equiv. 461). and a picrate, m.p. 238° (Found: N 17.6, S 5.4. $C_{12}H_{10}N_4S.C_6H_3N_3O_7$ requires N 16.9, S 5.2%). On boiling with conc. hydrochloric acid the product decomposed. *t.* butyl chloride, phenyl carbamide (m.p. and mixed m.p. 147°) and 2-amino-benzothiazole (m.p. 130°, picrate m.p. 265°) were identified amongst the products.

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